

**Critical elements that discriminate between successful and unsuccessful ERP
implementations in Sri Lanka**

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Citation:

Wickramasinghe, V., & Gunawardena, V. (2010). Critical elements that discriminate between successful and unsuccessful ERP implementations in Sri Lanka. Journal of Enterprise Information Management, 23(4), 466-485

This Version is available at: doi: 10.1108/17410391011061771

Purpose- To explore ERP implementation project performance of successful and unsuccessful implementations; critical elements (CEs) that conduce to success; and whether implementation project performance and CEs vary across the number of modules implemented, product type, and number of employees affected by the ERP.

Design/methodology/approach- Survey research methodology was used and collected data from 74 ERP implementation projects in Sri Lanka. Data were analysed using descriptive statistics, independent sample t-test, one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA), and logistic regression.

Findings- ERP implementation project performance significantly differs between successful and unsuccessful implementations. The importance given to CEs of training and education, user involvement, managing user expectations, interdepartmental cooperation, ERP teamwork and team composition, software development, testing and troubleshooting, project management, project champion, BPR and customisation, change management programme and culture, and effective communication significantly differ between successful and unsuccessful implementations. Although ERP implementation project performance does not vary by the number of ERP modules implemented, product type, and number of employees affected by the ERP, several CEs were found to vary by these three contextual variables.

Originality/value- Despite extensive literature on ERP implementations, empirical studies are needed for a better understanding of CEs that conduce to success. In the context of globalisation of business operations and interlocking supply chains, research on CEs that conduce to success in Sri Lanka is interesting, relevant and timely since there is an increasing interest in understanding work environment in Asia.

Keywords: enterprise resource planning; ERP implementation; critical elements.

Paper: Research paper

Introduction

An ERP system is an integrated enterprise computing system that lets an enterprise automate the flow of material, information, and financial resources among all functions within the enterprise on a common database, share common data and practices across the enterprise, and produce and access information in a real-time environment. It promises one database, one application, and a unified interface across the entire enterprise enabling it to

gain a holistic view of the business (Bingi *et al.*, 1999). Firms implement ERP systems as a means of reducing operating costs, enhancing competitiveness, increasing productivity and improving customer service (see Jang *et al.*, 2009; Mabert *et al.*, 2003; Zhang *et al.*, 2005).

However, the implementation of ERP systems is difficult and places tremendous demands on corporate time and resources (Al-Mashari *et al.*, 2003). Extant literature provides evidence that many ERP implementations have been classified as failures because they did not achieve predetermined corporate goals (see Bingi *et al.*, 1999; Zhang *et al.*, 2005). Given the high stakes involved, it is imperative for organisations embarking on enterprise system (ES) projects to have a better understanding of factors that conduce to success (see Loh and Koh, 2004). Therefore, this paper attempts to empirically identify factors that conduce to successful ERP implementations in an Asian developing country, Sri Lanka. In this study, we use the term “critical elements (CEs) to refer to these factors that conduce to success. For the study, quantitative research methodology was used and collected data from 74 ERP implementation projects in Sri Lanka.

Further, research on ESs has primarily examined experience of specific organisations that implemented enterprise systems, detailing a single case study of how they implemented the system in their organisation (e.g. Chien and Tsaur, 2007; Snider *et al.*, 2009; Woo, 2007; Yusuf *et al.*, 2004). While case studies provide insights into the impact of ES in specific situations, the lack of generalisability has hampered the development of theory or an overarching framework for interpreting and framing research applicable across organisations (Arnold, 2006). Hence, the need of rethinking the methodologies that are being applied in contemporary enterprise information system (EIS) research has been emphasized (see Arnold 2006). However, it is scarce to find empirical research studies based on survey research methodology that investigated CEs, which conduce to success, from ERP implementation project team members’ perspective. As detailed in methodology, data were collected from project team members engaged in 74 ERP implementation projects in Sri Lanka.

Further, literature on ERP or ESs originates from and describes application contexts of the developed countries in the West or countries in the Asia-Pacific region such as China and Taiwan (see Al-Mashari *et al.*, 2003; Hong and Kim, 2002). Extant literature suggests that valuable lessons could be learned from implementation experiences in different parts of the world (see Avison and Malaurent, 2007, Davison 2002, Sheu *et al.*, 2004, Soh *et al.* 2000). In response to several factors, such as increasing global competition, lower labour costs in Sri Lanka and inducements from the Sri Lankan government, the number of international businesses coming into the country has been increasing since the introduction of open economic policies in 1977. In the context of globalisation of business operations and interlocking supply chains, a research on ERP systems in South Asia (Sri Lanka in particular) is interesting, relevant and timely since relatively little is known about ERP implementations in this part of the world. For instance, our review of journals that are outlets for information systems related research in popular databases of Business Source Premier, ABI/Inform, Emerald, ScienceDirect, and Wiley Blackwell has been unable to find any studies conducted on ESs in developing countries, not even in India. The extent to which the research findings on ERP implementation contexts in North America, Western Europe as well as countries in the Asia-Pacific region could be generalized to the South Asian context has not been widely tested. Therefore, the research setting is both progressive and international in nature as the paper explores a timely issue while maintaining an international perspective of the Sri Lankan context situated in a global environment. From a practical standpoint, we believe that the findings of this exploratory study will be able to provide practitioners with valuable information that would enable them to make informed managerial decisions in a country that is considered as an active and promising destination for investment in the Asian region. On the other hand, the findings of this exploratory study will be able to establish baseline data and would be a source of general guidance in stimulating future research in this area.

In the above context, the specific aims of the study are to explore 1) ERP implementation project performance of successful and unsuccessful implementations, 2)

whether CEs that conduce to success differ between successful and unsuccessful implementations, and 3) whether implementation project performance and CEs vary across (a) number of modules implemented, (b) product type, and (c) number of employees affected by the ERP. Consistent with the objectives, in the next section theoretical background is briefly reviewed. This is followed by the methodology adopted. Thereafter, the main findings are presented and discussed. The paper concludes with a discussion on managerial implications of the findings and research areas for further inquiry and understanding.

Theoretical background

ERP implementation project performance

The specific literature on ERP implementations suggests that ERP implementation project performance is different from traditional information system success measures in that it is not evaluated by the end-users but by the project team members (Hong and Kim, 2002). Implementation project performance is frequently defined in terms of the achievement of some predetermined goals, which normally include multiple parameters such as clarity (e.g. DeLone and McLean, 2003), accuracy (e.g. Wu and Wang, 2007), timelines (e.g. Bailey and Pearson, 1983; Wu and Wang 2007), content (e.g. DeLone and McLean, 2003), system stability (e.g. Wu and Wang, 2007), flexibility (e.g. Bailey and Pearson, 1983), reliability (e.g. Wu and Wang, 2007; Yusuf *et al.*, 2004), project is completed within time and budget (e.g. Al-Mashari *et al.* 2003, Hong and Kim, 2002), and the achievement of the business case/predetermined corporate goals (e.g. Hong and Kim, 2002). Appendix A summarises ERP implementation project performance measures mentioned in literature. However, most studies that measured ERP implementation performance used only one or two surrogates of ERP implementation performance (e.g. Ang *et al.*, 2002; Burns and Turnipseed, 1991; Mabert *et al.*, 2003; Umble *et al.*, 2003; Zhang *et al.*, 2005). Given the empirical and anecdotal evidence that indicate ERP implementation project performance (refer to Appendix A) would vary between successful and unsuccessful implementations, for this study, it is hypothesised:

Hypothesis 1: There will be significant differences in ERP implementation project performance between successful and unsuccessful ERP implementations, where project performance will be high in successful implementations.

Critical elements

Appendix B summarises CEs that can be commonly found in literature. To make the review of CEs complete, following sections describe briefly CEs and their importance in ERP implementations.

ERP vendors use different hardware platforms, databases, and operating systems; certain ERP packages are only compatible with certain databases and operation systems (Zhang *et al.*, 2005). Therefore, ERP literature identifies the need of software development, testing and troubleshooting as vital ingredients in ERP implementations (e.g. Bingi *et al.*, 1999; Wee, 2000). Further, implementing an ERP system involves reengineering the existing business processes to the best business process standard (Mandal and Gunasekaran, 2002). ERP packages provide generic off-the-shelf business and software solutions; more or less they cannot fully meet specific requirements of a firm, especially when the business processes of the firm are unique. Therefore, business process reengineering and minimum customisation are identified as important factors that conduce to success (e.g. Holland and Light, 1999; Roberts and Barrar, 1992; Sumner, 1999). Furthermore, continuous monitoring and evaluation of performance are also identified as critical in ERP implementations (e.g. Falkowski *et al.*, 1998; Holland and Light, 1999).

Many studies stressed the importance of top management support as a vital ingredient in ERP implementations as ERP implementations usually trigger profound changes in organizational culture and business practices (e.g. Bingi *et al.*, 1999; Wee, 2000; Zhang *et al.*, 2005). Further, ERP implementations require key people throughout the organization to create a clear, compelling vision of how it should operate in order to satisfy customers, empower employees, and facilitate suppliers (e.g. Falkowski *et al.*, 1998; Holland

and Light, 1999; Wee, 2000). Furthermore, several studies highlighted the requirement of change management and understanding of cultural context in implementing ERP systems (e.g. Bingi *et al.*, 1999; Holland and Light, 1999). Notwithstanding the claims to flexibility, ERP products have their specific preferred business model, which dictates the manner of doing business. The existing organisational structure, culture and processes found in many firms may not be compatible with the structure, tools, and types of information provided by the ERP system. In order to take advantage of ERP software, firms need to adapt the new model and, correspondingly, change themselves. The resulting changes may significantly affect organisational structures, policies, processes, and how employees perform their jobs. Moreover, lack of user education and training, and user involvement in ERP implementations are identified as leading to failure (e.g. Sum *et al.*, 1997; Yusuf *et al.*, 2004).

Project champion is identified as linked to the success of technological innovations as project champion performs the crucial function of transformational leadership (see Falkowski *et al.*, 1998; Sum *et al.*, 1997). Further, successful ERP implementations require excellent project management (Falkowski *et al.*, 1998; Holland and Light, 1999; Wee, 2000). This includes a clear definition of objectives, development of work and resource plans, and careful tracking of project progress (see Umble *et al.*, 2003). Furthermore, factors such as teamwork and composition (e.g. Falkowski *et al.*, 1998; Koh *et al.*, 2008; Rosario, 2000; Somers and Nelson, 2001; Wee, 2000), effective communication (e.g. Falkowski *et al.*, 1998; Sum *et al.*, 1997; Wee, 2000), appropriate business and legacy systems (e.g. Holland and Light, 1999; Roberts and Barrar, 1992), interdepartmental co-operation, interdepartmental communication, and management of expectations (e.g. Somers and Nelson, 2001) are also identified as critical in ERP implementations. Given the empirical and anecdotal evidence that indicate the importance given to CEs would vary between successful and unsuccessful ERP implementations, for this study, it is hypothesised:

Hypothesis 2: There will be significant differences in the importance given to CEs by successful and unsuccessful ERP implementations, where the importance given will be high in successful implementations.

Contextual factors

The relationship between contextual factors of an organisation and their impact on various operations has been studied for a long time (Mabert *et al.*, 2003). The impact of organisational size on adoption, implementation and use of information technologies has received increasing attention in the academic literature (see Federici, 2009; Ifinedo, 2007; Laukkanen *et al.*, 2007). An organisation's size is defined in ERP literature in terms of annual revenue (e.g. Mabert *et al.*, 2003); number of employees (e.g. Federici, 2009; Laukkanen *et al.*, 2007; Raymond and Uwizeyemungu, 2007; Soja, 2006); and a composite index between turnover and number of employees (e.g. Buonanno *et al.*, 2005). However, some scholars did not specify the criteria adopted in defining an organisation's size (e.g. Shiau *et al.*, 2009).

Another contextual factor is product type, i.e., off-the-shelf or customised (e.g. Light, 2005). The common view, particularly the one espoused by vendors, however, is that ERP implementations are successful when the standard model is adopted. Yet, customisation occurs due to misalignment between functionality of the package and requirements of those in the implementing organisation (see Light, 2005). In the analysis of packaged software implementations, Lucas *et al.* (1988) suggest that package implementation is different from custom implementation. Given the empirical and anecdotal evidence that indicate contextual factors influence ERP implementation project performance and the importance of CEs, hypotheses for the study are composite:

Hypothesis 3: There will be significant differences in ERP implementation project performance by (a) number of ERP modules implemented, (b) product type, and (c) number of employees affected by the ERP.

Hypothesis 4: There will be significant differences in the importance given to CEs by (a) number of ERP modules implemented, (b) product type, and (c) number of employees affected by the ERP.

Research methods

Sample and data collection

The list of firms that implemented ERP systems was obtained from a firm that conducted a comprehensive market survey on ERP systems in use in Sri Lanka. The list contained 90 firms belonging to the private sector operating in Sri Lanka. The specific literature on ERP system implementation success suggests that ERP implementation success is different from traditional information system success measure in that it should be evaluated by the project team members (see Hong and Kim 2002). Hence, our study examined CEs that conduce to success from project team members' perspective.

Data were collected from one of the randomly selected main persons who have been involved in the ERP implementation project as a project-team member in each firm. For this 90 contact persons were identified from each firm. Contact persons were instructed to distribute the link to the on-line survey to a randomly selected ERP system implementation project team member via e-mail. At the beginning of the questionnaire, instructions of filling the survey was provided along with the purpose of the research and ensured confidentiality. Although 82 records were saved on the database from the on-line link, eight records were considered incomplete and had to be discarded. This left 74 valid responses, a response rate of 82 per cent of the original sample. When considering the education level of the respondents, all the respondents have either Bachelors degree or a postgraduate degree as the highest level of education. The profile of the firms and respondents are shown in Table 1.

Take in Table I

Measures

The scope of the study is limited to ERP implementation issues after the purchase of ERP hardware and software. Although one could argue that ERP implementation is a never-

ending cycle of continuous improvement, the focus of this study is on initial implementation efforts, and immediate success results achieved from those efforts (e.g. Sun *et al.*, 2005).

The measures for ERP implementation project performance and CEs were developed based on the previously reviewed related literature (refer to Appendix A and Appendix B). For the purpose of the study, both sets of variables were defined broadly. Sample measures used for ERP implementation project performance are: “Accuracy of the system: data accuracy (no change of data) between the business processes”; “Clarity of the system: information provided by the system conveys the intended meaning”; and “Stability of the system: data robustness (no loss of data) between the business processes”. As detailed in sample and data collection, respondents of the survey were persons who have been involved in an ERP implementation project as a project-team member. Hence, project-team members’ awareness of the meanings of ERP system implementation project performance measures and CEs were considered as an advantage. Where available, scale items from existing research were used. For the constructs that did not have readily available scale items, appropriate scale items were developed using guidelines recommended by Nunnally (1978). In doing so, first, the domain of the relevant construct was specified. Then, items were developed to map the construct’s conceptual definition. All constructs of ERP implementation project performance and CEs were measured on a five-point Likert scale ranging from 1 (very low) to 5 (very high). The items were pre-tested on a convenience sample of 10 implementation project team members that fitted with the intended sample of the study and revised accordingly. Standardised Cronbach’s alpha of the scale was examined and principal-components factor analysis (Varimax rotation) was conducted. The criteria adhered to are: eigenvalues of all components should not be less than 1.0; loadings should be 0.50 or greater to be considered practically significant; cronbach's alpha values of each factor extracted and overall measure should be greater than 0.7 (see Hair *et al.* 1998). The items of each factor were averaged to produce a mean score for the each construct (refer to Table II and III).

ERP implementation project success. The measure consisted of 7-items and had a reliability of 0.798 (refer to Appendix C). Factor analysis yielded one factor, where Eigenvalue=4.47 and Explained variation=67%. The items were averaged to produce a mean score for the construct. The results of the factor analysis are shown in Table II.

Take in Table II

Critical elements. The measure consisted of 16 items and had a reliability of 0.745 (refer to Appendix C). Factor analysis yielded a set of three factors, which explained 77 per cent (76.76) of the variance. The standardised estimates and reliability statistics for these factors are provided in Table III.

Take in Table III

Overall success of implementation. To determine the extent to which ERP project implementation is perceived to be successful one global item on dichotomous scale (yes/no) was used. Successful implementation was coded as “1” and unsuccessful implementation was coded as “0”.

Contextual variables. Data on product type, number of modules implemented, and number of employees affected by the ERP implementation were collected as categorical variables.

Method of data analysis

Data were analysed using descriptive statistics, independent sample t-test, one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA), and logistic regression. To determine the extent to which ERP implementation project performance and CEs correlate with overall success of

implementation, responses for the global measure was used. However, the interrelationships between CEs are beyond the focus of this study and have not been explored as a result.

Results and discussion

ERP implementation project performance and overall success of ERP implementation

The results of the ERP implementation project performance and overall success of the ERP implementation are shown in Table IV. Of the 74 firms, 42 per cent (N=31) identified their implementations as successful while 58 per cent (N=43) identified as unsuccessful. The results are shown in Table IV. The ERP implementation project performance (overall) was obtained by averaging the items of the construct. The differences in ERP implementation project performance by overall success of ERP implementation was analysed using t-test. Results are shown in Table IV. As can be seen from Table IV, overall ERP implementation project performance differs significantly between successful and unsuccessful implementations, where implementation project performance is high in successful projects. This supports H1.

Take in Table IV

Table V shows descriptive statistics and zero-order correlations among study variables.

Take in Table V

Differences in ERP implementation project performance by contextual factors. The differences in overall ERP implementation project performance by product type, the number of modules implemented, and the number of employees affected by the ERP were analysed using t-test and ANOVA, appropriately. Results are shown in Table VI. As can be seen from Table VI, implementation project performance does not vary by the number of modules

implemented, product type, and number of employees affected by the ERP. Hence, H3 is not supported.

Take in Table VI

Differences in CEs

Whether the importance given for CEs varies by overall success of ERP implementation, product type, the number of modules implemented, and the number of employees affected by the ERP were analysed using t-test and ANOVA, appropriately. Results are shown in Table VII. CE Factor 1 and CE Factor 3 show significant differences by successful and unsuccessful implementations, where the importance given for CE Factor 1 and CE Factor 3 is high in successful implementations. However, the importance given for CE Factor 2 does not vary by successful and unsuccessful implementations. Hence, H2 is partially supported.

The importance of CE Factor 1 and CE Factor 2 vary by product type, where the importance of CE Factor 1 and CE Factor 2 is high in off-the-shelf product implementations. Further, the importance of CE Factor 2 and CE Factor 3 vary by the number of modules implemented, where the importance of CE Factor 2 and CE Factor 3 is high when the number of modules implemented are more than 10. However, there are no significant differences in the importance given to CEs by the number of employees affected by the ERP. Hence, H4 is partially supported.

Take in Table VII

Critical elements that discriminate between successful and unsuccessful ERP implementations

The results of the logistic regression are shown in Table VIII. Nagelkerke R^2 was 0.860 suggesting that 86 per cent of the variance is explained by the covariates. P value of 0.591 of Hosmer and Lemeshow test suggests a good fit. The overall percentage of cases correctly classified is 85 (84.5%). It is evident that CE Factor 1 and CE Factor 3 are important CEs that discriminate between successful and unsuccessful implementations. For instance, the odds of successful implementations to perceive higher level of importance in CE Factor 1 (as opposed to unsuccessful implementations) are almost 10 times (10.39) as high.

Take in Table VIII

Conclusions and implications

In ESs literature, it is very rare to find empirical surveys on ERP or ESs. This study presented results of a study that surveyed 74 ERP implementation projects in Sri Lanka to investigate CEs and contextual variables that discriminate between successful and unsuccessful implementations.

We have used widely accepted multiple parameters drawn from literature to evaluate ERP implementation project performance. The 7-item measure used in this study was empirically based and was shown to be valid and reliable in the Sri Lankan context. Similarly, the item measures used to evaluate CEs that conduce to successful ERP implementations were drawn from the extant literature. Factor analysis yielded three components and these were shown to be valid and reliable in the Sri Lankan context.

The first objective of the study was to explore whether ERP implementation project performance differs between successful and unsuccessful implementations. It was found that implementation project performance differs significantly between successful and unsuccessful implementations. Similar to previous studies, this study also identified that system stability (e.g. Wu and Wang, 2007) and project is completed within time and budget

(e.g. Al-Mashari *et al.*, 2003, Hong and Kim, 2002) are major concerns in evaluating ERP implementation project performance. Although previous studies identified clarity (e.g. DeLone and McLean, 2003), accuracy (e.g. Wu and Wang, 2007), timelines (e.g. Bailey and Pearson, 1983; Wu and Wang, 2007), and content (e.g. DeLone and McLean, 2003) of the ERP system as significant aspects that could discriminate successful implementations from unsuccessful implementations, findings of our study does not support such claims.

The second objective of the study was to examine whether CEs that conduce to success differ between successful and unsuccessful implementations. It was found that CE Factor 1 and CE Factor 3 significantly differ between successful and unsuccessful implementations. CE Factor 1 comprised of user training and education, user involvement, managing user expectations, interdepartmental cooperation, ERP teamwork and composition, software development, testing and troubleshooting, project management, project champion, and BPR and customisation. CE Factor 3 comprised of change management programme and culture, and effective communication. Hence, the findings established the importance of the dimensions that comprise of CE Factor 1 and CE Factor 3 for the ERP implementation success in Sri Lanka. Previous studies (such as Holland and Light 1999, Rosario 2000, Somers and Nelson 2001, Yusuf et al. 2004, and also refer to Appendix B) also suggested the importance of these elements in ERP implementations. However, we have not come across previous empirical studies based on quantitative methodology that investigated how importance given to these CEs differs between successful and unsuccessful implementations to make straight forward comparisons. Therefore, considerable research is necessary to validate the links suggested in this study. The current study represents a step in that direction.

The third objective of the study was to examine whether ERP implementation project performance and CEs differ by the number of modules implemented, product type, and the number of employees affected by the ERP. It was found that implementation project performance does not differ by any of these variables. However, the importance of CE Factor 1 and CE Factor 2 vary by product type, where the importance of these factors is high in off-the-shelf product implementations. The importance of CE Factor 2 and CE Factor 3

vary by the number of modules implemented, where the importance of these factors is high when the number of modules implemented are more than 10. However, there are no significant differences in the importance given to CEs by the number of employees affected by the ERP. We have not come across previous empirical studies that investigated how the product type, number of modules implemented, and number of employees influence ERP implementations to make straight forward comparisons with our results. However, previous researchers (such as Ifinedo 2007, Laukkanen *et al.* 2007, Light 2005) also suggested the importance of these contextual factors in ERP implementations.

Overall, the findings of our study, which was conducted by surveying 74 ERP implementation projects in Sri Lanka, revealed that ERP implementation project performance significantly differs between successful and unsuccessful implementations. The importance given to CEs of training and education, user involvement, managing user expectations, interdepartmental cooperation, ERP teamwork and composition, software development, testing and troubleshooting, project management, project champion, BPR and customisation, change management programme and culture, and effective communication significantly differ between successful and unsuccessful implementations. Furthermore, ERP implementation project performance does not vary by product type, the number of modules implemented, and the number of employees affected by the ERP. However, several CEs were found to vary by these three contextual variables. Therefore, the insight given by the findings of this study could be utilised as a diagnostic tool in the better understanding of CEs surrounding ERP implementations. Practitioners could use the findings to analyse and assess issues in connection to ERP implementations to take necessary corrective actions to achieve project success. The study also provides valuable information to firms that are either embarking on or considering ERP implementations to better prepare themselves for a successful implementation of the system.

Limitations and directions for future research

This research focused on a limited number of variables for ERP implementation project performance and CEs, and used perceived measures to evaluate these. The factual data of success outcomes were left out due to the difficulty in securing these from the participating organisations. Further, data were collected from one of the randomly selected main persons who have been involved in the ERP implementation project as a project-team member in each firm. It would be an advantage if we could have collected data from several members in a project team. Furthermore, the importance of CEs may change over the course of ERP implementation because of the dynamics of the project life cycle. However, as an initial attempt we did not explore the stage of the project life cycle. Factor analysis yielded three factors for the item measure used to evaluate CEs. However, the validity of a measure cannot be truly established on the basis of a single cross-sectional study. The validation of a measure requires the assessment of measurement properties over a variety of samples in similar and different contexts. Hence, future research, in different samples and longitudinal studies, are necessary that compliment questionnaire surveys with interviews and secondary data. Moreover, future research can move beyond listing CEs and could explore the interrelationships between them.

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Tables

Table I. Profile of the firms and respondents (N=74)

	%		%
<i>Industrial sector</i>		<i>Number of modules implemented</i>	
Manufacturing	35	Less than 5	41
Telecommunication	27	5 - 10	43
Trade and Logistics	11	More than 10	16
Hotels and Travel	8		
Diversified Holdings	7	<i>Frequently implemented modules</i>	
Power and Energy	7	Financial accounting	93
Financial services	5	Materials management	82
		Sales and distribution	73
<i>Number of employees affected</i>		Maintenance	47
More than 1001	45	HR	39
501-1000	27		
Less than 500	28	<i>ERP use durations</i>	
		Less than 3 years	59
<i>ERP vendor</i>		3 - 5 years	27
SAP	37	More than 5 years	14
IFS	30		
Oracle	14	<i>Respondents' experience with</i>	
Other	19	<i>ERP implementations</i>	
		Less than 5 years	64
<i>Product type</i>		5 - 10 years	29
Customised	69	More than 10 years	7
Off-the-shelf	31		

Table II. Summarised results of factor analysis - ERP implementation project performance

The project is completed within budget	.811
The project is completed within the scheduled time	.561
Clarity of the system	.675
Accuracy of the system	.919
Timeliness of the system	.841
Stability of the system	.583
Achievement of the business case	.701
Explained variation	67.3%
Eigenvalue	4.47
Standardised Cronbach's alpha	.798
Mean	3.67
S.D.	.58

Table III. Summarised results of factor analysis - CEs

	CE Factor 1	CE Factor 2	CE Factor 3
User training and education	.804		
User involvement	.683		
Managing user expectations	.643		
Interdepartmental cooperation	.602		
ERP teamwork and composition	.596		
Software development, testing and troubleshooting	.569		
Project management	.555		
Project champion	.543		
BPR and customisation	.515		
Business plan and vision		.769	
Top management support		.667	
Monitoring and evaluation of performance		.563	
Clear roles and responsibilities		.481	
Appropriate business and IT legacy systems		.434	
Change management programme and culture			.663
Effective communication			.640
Explained variation	51.77	16.89	8.09
Eigenvalue	6.72	2.19	1.05
Standardised Cronbach's alpha	.80	.81	.82
Mean	3.37	3.19	2.91
S.D.	.69	.94	.90

Table IV. ERP implementation project performance

	Total (N=74) Mean Median (SD)	Successful (N=31) Mean Median (SD)	Unsuccessful (N=43) Mean Median (SD)	t	Sig (2- tailed)
The project is completed within budget	3.25 4.00 (1.06)	4.08 4.00 (.27)	2.72 2.00 (1.05)	-7.69	.000***
The project is completed within the scheduled time	2.77 2.50 (1.01)	3.36 3.00 (.82)	2.34 2.00 (.90)	-4.65	.000***
Clarity of the system	3.86 4.00 (0.69)	3.97 4.00 (.71)	3.79 4.00 (.68)	-1.08	.281
Accuracy of the system	3.86 4.00 (.75)	3.87 4.00 (.68)	3.86 4.00 (.80)	-.03	.973
Timeliness of the system	4.03 4.00 (.74)	4.13 4.00 (.57)	3.95 4.00 (.84)	-1.01	.313
Stability of the system	3.94 4.00 (.62)	4.10 4.00 (.48)	3.84 4.00 (.68)	-1.79	.076*
Achievement of the business case	3.79 4.00 (.76)	3.97 4.00 (.61)	3.67 4.00 (.83)	-1.62	.108
<i>ERP implementation performance</i>		3.92	3.49	-3.39	.001**

Note: * p<0.05; **p<0.01; ***p<0.001

Table V. Correlations

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
1 Successful/Unsuccessful	1						
2 Product type	-.290*	1					
3 Number of modules implemented	.154	-.244*	1				
4 Number of employees affected	-.028	-.186	-.049	1			
5 ERP implementation performance	.373**	.064	.189	-.193	1		
6 CE Factor 1	.606**	-.355**	.248*	-.191	.519**	1	
7 CE Factor 2	.015	-.367**	.327**	-.024	-.045	.190	1
8 CE Factor 3	.373**	-.189	.373**	-.153	.606**	.308**	.282*

* significant at the 0.05 level, ** significant at the 0.01 level.

Table VI. ERP implementation performance by product type, number of modules implemented and number of employees affected

	Product type		<i>t</i>	Sig. (t-test)	Number of modules implemented			<i>F</i>	Sig. (ANOVA)	Number of employees affected			<i>F</i>	Sig. (ANOVA)
	Off-the-shelf	Customised			<5	5-10	>10			<500	500-1000	>1000		
	Mean	Mean			Mean	Mean	Mean			Mean	Mean	Mean		
ERP implementation performance	3.62	3.70	-.54	.593	3.53	3.65	4.02	2.98	.057	3.85	3.69	3.55	1.68	.194

Table VII. CE s by overall success of ERP implementation, product type, number of modules implemented and number of employees affected

CEs	Overall ERP success		<i>t</i>	Sig. (t-test)	Product type		<i>t</i>	Sig. (t-test)	Number of modules implemented			<i>F</i>	Sig. (ANOVA)	Number of employees affected			<i>F</i>	Sig. (ANOVA)
	Successful	Unsuccessful			Off-the-shelf	Customised			<5	5-10	>10			<500	500-1000	>1000		
	Mean	Mean			Mean	Mean			Mean	Mean	Mean			Mean	Mean	Mean		
CE Factor 1	3.87	3.02	-6.37	.000***	3.75	3.23	3.13	.003**	3.17	3.45	3.70	2.73	.072	3.53	3.43	3.22	1.39	.254
CE Factor 2	3.21	3.18	-.12	.903	3.71	2.96	3.25	.002**	2.82	3.39	3.55	4.11	.021*	3.15	3.25	3.15	.06	.937
CE Factor 3	3.30	2.62	-3.34	.001**	3.18	2.82	1.57	.121	2.50	3.05	3.45	6.38	.003**	3.02	3.03	2.75	.80	.453

Note: * p<0.05; **p<0.01; ***p<0.001

Table VIII. Summarised results of logistic regression

	Coefficient	S.E.	Wald	P-value	Odds Ratio
CE Factor 1	2.341	.619	14.314	.000***	10.392
CE Factor 3	.105	.420	.063	.047*	1.111
Constant	-8.778	2.019	18.895	.000***	.000

Note: * p<0.05; ***p<0.001.

Appendix A: ERP implementation project performance

Item	Author(s)	Al-Mashari et al. (2003)	Ang et al. (2002)	Bailey and Pearson (1983)	Burns and Turnipseed (1991)	DeLone and McLean (2003)	Hong and Kim (2002)	Mabert et al. (2003)	Mandal and Gunasekaran (2002)	Markus et al. (2000)	Umble et al. (2003)	Wang et al. 2005	Wu and Wang (2007)	Yusuf et al. (2004)	Zhang et al. (2005)
Accuracy						√							√		
Clarity						√									
Content of the system						√									
Flexibility				√										√	√
Intended business performance improvement/ achievement of predetermined corporate goals	√						√		√	√	√	√		√	
On time	√						√	√				√			
Reliability				√									√	√	√
System acceptance and usage			√											√	
System stability												√	√		
Timeliness/response time				√									√	√	√
User satisfaction	√	√			√				√	√				√	
Within budget	√						√	√				√			

Appendix B: Critical elements

Item	Author(s)	Bingi <i>et al.</i> (1999)	Buckhout <i>et al.</i> (1999)	Duchessi <i>et al.</i> (1989)	Ehie & Madsen (2005)	Falkowski <i>et al.</i> (1998)	Holland & Light (1999)	Mandal & Gunasekaran (2002)	Manthou <i>et al.</i> (1996)	Roberts & Barrar (1992)	Rosario (2000)	Somers & Nelson (2001)	Sum <i>et al.</i> (1997)	Sumner (1999)	Wee (2000)	Yusuf <i>et al.</i> (2004)
Appropriate business and IT legacy systems																
BPR and minimum customisation		√			√		√	√		√	√			√	√	√
Business plan and vision			√	√		√	√			√	√	√			√	
Change management programme and culture		√		√		√	√		√	√	√			√	√	
Effective Communication				√		√	√				√		√	√	√	
Interdepartmental corporation												√				
Managing user expectations												√				
Monitoring and evaluation of performance						√	√		√	√	√		√	√		
Project champion				√		√					√	√	√	√		
Project management				√	√	√	√		√		√	√		√	√	
Project team competence, composition and team work		√	√			√	√				√	√		√	√	
Software development, testing and troubleshooting		√					√				√				√	
Top management support		√	√	√	√		√			√		√		√	√	√
User involvement								√								√
User training and education					√			√					√			√

Appendix C: Measures

ERP implementation project performance:

The project is completed within budget.
The project is completed within the scheduled time.
Clarity of the system
Accuracy of the system
Timeliness of the system
Stability of the system
Achievement of the business case

Critical elements:

Software development, testing and troubleshooting
Project management
BPR and customisation
Change management programme and culture
Monitoring and evaluation of performance
Business plan and vision
Appropriate business and IT legacy systems
User training and education
User involvement
Interdepartmental cooperation
Clear roles and responsibilities
Managing user expectations
Top management support
ERP teamwork and composition
Project champion
Effective communication